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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF METFORMIN
HYDROCHLORIDE SUSTAINED RELEASE TABLETS**

Vardha Shirisha*¹, Dr.K. Nagasree, Dr.K. Shrivankumar, Dr.k. Chaitanyaprasad
Department Of Pharmaceutics, Samskruti College Of Pharmacy In Ghatkesar, Telangana.
501301.

Abstract:

The aim of present is to develop & evaluate sustained release matrix tablet of Metformin hydrochloride. Metformin hydrochloride is the first-line medication for the treatment of type 2 diabetes, particularly in people who are overweight. It is also used in the treatment of polycystic ovary syndrome. It is not associated with weight gain and is taken by mouth. In present study, an attempt has been made to develop sustained release matrix tablet of Metformin hydrochloride thereby reducing its frequency of administration & other dose related side effects. Different types of Gaur gum, Eudragit and Xanthan gum were used as polymers. Total 9 formulations were prepared in trial batches. The formulation was evaluated for various pre compression & post compression parameters. All the formulations showed compliance with the pharmacopoeial standards. On the basis of evaluated parameters formulation F6 was considered to be the best one. Formulation F6 containing polymer Eudragit showed 98.72 % invitro drug release profile. The release data for formulation F6 was fitted to various mathematical models like zero order, first order, Krosmeier Peppas & Higuchi model. It was observed that drug follows Higuchi release mechanism.

Keywords: Metformin hydrochloride, Gaur gum, Eudragit and Xanthan gum, Sustained release tablets.

Corresponding author:

Vardha Shirisha*,
Department of Pharmaceutics,
Samskruti College Of Pharmacy,
Ghatkesar, Telangana.
Email Id- vardhashirishagoud@gmail.com

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Sustained release dosage form is mainly designed for the maintenance of therapeutic blood concentration of the drug for extended period of time with minimum systemic adverse effects. The drugs having a low therapeutic index and short elimination half-life are preferred for preparation of sustained released formulations .

Introduction of matrix tablet as sustained release (SR) has given a new breakthrough for novel drug delivery system (NDDS) in the field of Pharmaceutical technology. It excludes complex production procedures such as coating and pelletization during manufacturing and drug release rate from the dosage form is controlled mainly by the type and proportion of polymer used in the preparations. Hydrophilic polymer matrix is widely used for formulating an SR dosage form. Because of increased complication and expense involved in marketing of new drug entities, has focused greater attention on development of sustained release or controlled release drug delivery systems. Matrix systems are widely used for the purpose of sustained release. It is the release system which prolongs and controls the release of the drug that is dissolved or dispersed. In fact, a matrix is defined as a well mixed composite of one or more drugs with gelling agent i.e. hydrophilic polymers. oral route has been one of the most popular routes of drug delivery due to its ease of administration, patient compliance, least sterility constraints and flexible design of dosage forms. Time release technology, also known as sustained release (SR) sustained action (SA), extended release (ER, XR or XL), time-release or timed-release, controlled-release (CR), modified release (MR) or continuous-release (CR) is a mechanism used in pill tablet or capsules to dissolve slowly and release a drug over a prolonged period of time. Matrix system is widely used for the purpose of sustained release. It is the system which prolongs and controls the release of drug that is dissolved or dispersed. Matrix Tablets A matrix system consists of active and inactive ingredients that are homogeneously dispersed and mixed in the dosage form. It is by far the most commonly used oral extended release technology and the popularity of the matrix systems can be attributed to several factors. The release from matrix type formulations is governed by Fick's first law of diffusion. In a matrix system the drug is dispersed as solid particles within a porous matrix formed of a hydrophobic polymer (such as wax, polyethylene, polypropylene, and ethyl cellulose) or hydrophilic polymer (such as hydroxy propyl cellulose, hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose, methylcellulose, sodium carboxy methylcellulose, alginates and scleroglucan). In this sense, the term

“matrix” indicates the three dimensional network containing the drug and other substances such as solvents and excipients required for the specific preparation. Matrix drug delivery systems release the drug in continuous manner. These release the drug by both dissolution controlled as well as diffusion controlled mechanisms. Initially, drug particles located at the surface of the release unit will be dissolved and the drug released rapidly. Thereafter, drug particles at successively increasing distances from the surface of the release unit will be dissolved and released by diffusion in the pores to the exterior of the release unit. In this system the drug reservoir is prepared by homogeneously dispersing drug particles in a rate controlling polymer matrix fabricated from either a lipophilic or a hydrophilic polymer. The drug is dispersed in the polymer matrix either by blending a therapeutic dose of finely ground drug particles with a liquid polymer or a highly viscous base polymer, followed by cross-linking of the polymer chain, mixing drug and polymer at an elevated temperature. It can also be fabricated by dissolving the drug and the polymer in a common solvent, followed by solvent evaporation at an elevated temperature and/or under a vacuum. The rate of drug release from this polymer matrix diffusion – controlled drug delivery system is time dependent and is defined at steady state by

$$Q/t^{1/2} = (2ACRDp)^{1/2}$$

Where, A is the initial loading drug dose in the polymer matrix;

CR is the drug reservoir concentration in the system;

Dp is the diffusivity of the drug molecules in the polymer matrix.

Drug release is controlled by controlling the loading dose, polymer solubility of drug and its diffusivity in the polymer matrix and the porosity of the release unit

Sustained release dosage forms are designed to release a drug at a predetermined rate by maintaining a constant drug level for a specific period of time with minimum side effects. The basic rationale of sustained release drug delivery system optimizes the biopharmaceutical, pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamics properties of a drug in such a way that its utility is maximized, side-effects are reduced and cure/treatment of the disease is¹ achieved. Introduction of matrix tablet as sustained release (SR) has given a new breakthrough for novel drug delivery system (NDDS) in the field of pharmaceutical technology. It excludes complex production procedures such as coating and pelletization during manufacturing and drug release rate from the dosage

form is controlled mainly by the type and proportion of polymer used in the preparations. Hydrophilic polymer matrix is widely used for formulating an SR dosage form. Oral sustained release (SR) products provide an advantage over conventional dosage forms by optimizing bio-pharmaceutics, pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics properties of drugs in such a way that it reduce dosing frequency to an extent that once daily dose is sufficient for penetration, polymer² swelling, drug dissolution, drug diffusion and matrix erosion. The materials most widely used in preparing matrix systems include both hydrophilic and hydrophobic polymers. Commonly available hydrophilic polymers include Hydroxypropylmethylcellulose (HPMC), Hydroxypropylcellulose (HPC), Hydroxyethyl cellulose (HEC), Xanthan gum, Sodium alginate, Poly (ethylene oxide) and cross-linked homo polymers and copolymers of acrylic acid³.

A typical peak-valley plasma concentration time profile is obtained which makes attainment of steady state condition difficult. Sustained-release oral delivery systems are designed to achieve therapeutically effective concentrations of drug in the systemic circulation over an extended period of time. Possible therapeutic benefits of a properly designed SR dosage form include low cost, simple processing, improved efficacy, reduced adverse events, flexibility in terms of the range of release profiles attainable, increased convenience and patient compliance.

Sustained release, sustained action, prolonged action controlled release, extended release, depot release these are the various terms used to identify drug delivery systems that are designed to achieve a prolonged therapeutic effect by continuously releasing medication over a long period of time after administration of a single dose of drug. The goal in designing sustained release delivery systems is to reduce frequency of dosing or to increase effectiveness of the drug by localization at the site of the action, reducing dose required or providing uniform drug delivery. The ideal drug delivery systems have two things would be required first it would be a single dose the duration of treatment whether it is for days or week, as with infection, or for the life time of the patient, as in hypertension or diabetes. Second it should deliver the active entity directly to the site of the action, thereby minimizing side effects.

PARAMETERS FOR DRUG TO BE FORMULATED IN SUSTAINED RELEASE DOSAGE FORM:

Physico-chemical parameters for drug selection.

1. Molecular weight/size < 1000 Daltons.
2. Solubility > 0.1 mg/ml for pH 1 to pH 7.8.
3. Apparent partition coefficient High.
4. Absorption mechanism Diffusion.
5. General absorbability from all GI segments.
6. Release should not be influenced by pH and enzymes.

Pharmacokinetic parameters for drug selection

1. Elimination half-life preferably between 2 to 8 hrs
2. Total clearance should not be dose dependent
3. Elimination rate constant required for design
4. Apparent volume of distribution (Vd) The larger Vd and MEC, the larger will be the required dose size
5. Absolute bioavailability should be 75% or more
6. Intrinsic absorption rate must be greater than release rate
7. Therapeutic concentration C_{ss} The lower C_{ss} and smaller Vd, the loss among of drug required.
8. Toxic concentration Apart the values of MTC and MEC, safer the dosage form. Also suitable for drugs with very short half-life.

FACTORS AFFECTING THE ORAL SUSTAIN RELEASE DOSAGE FORM DESIGN

A) Pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics factor:

1. Biological half-life

Drug with biological half-life of 2-8 hours are considered suitable candidate for sustain release dosage form, since this can reduce dosing frequency. However this is limited in that drugs with very short biological half lives may require excessive large amounts of drug in each dosage unit to maintain sustained effects, forcing the dosage form itself to become limitingly large.

2. Absorption

Rate of absorption of a sustained formulating depends upon release rate constant of the drug from the dosage form, and for the drugs that are absorbed by active transport the absorption is limited to intestine.

3. Distribution

The distribution of drugs into tissues can be important factor in the overall drug elimination kinetics. Since it not only lowers the concentration of circulating drug but it also can be rate limiting in its equilibrium with blood and extra vascular tissue, consequently apparent volume of distribution assumes different values depending n the time course of drug disposition. Thus for design of sustain release products, one must have information of disposition of drug.

4. Metabolism

The metabolic conversion to a drug is to be considered before converting into another form. Since as long as the location, rate, and extent of metabolism are known a successful sustain release product can be developed.

B) Drug properties relevant to sustain release formulation:

1. Dose size

A dose size of 500-1000mg is considered maximal for a conventional dosage form. This also holds true for sustain release dosage forms. Since dose size consideration serves to be a parameter for the safety involved in administration of large amounts with narrow therapeutic range.

2. Ionization, pka and aqueous solubility

Most drugs are weak acids or bases and in order for a drug to get absorbed, it must dissolve in the aqueous phase surrounding the site of administration and then partition into the absorbing membrane.

3. Partition coefficient

Bioavailability of a drug is largely influenced by the partition coefficient, as the biological membrane lipophilic in nature transport of drug across the membrane largely depends upon the partition coefficient of the drug. Drugs having low partition coefficient are considered as poor candidate for the sustain release formulation as it will be localized in the aqueous phase eg: Barbituric acid and vice a versa.

4. Drug stability

When drugs are orally administered, they come across acid-base hydrolysis and enzymatic degradation. In this case, if the drug is unstable in stomach, drug release system which provides medication over extended period of time is preferred, whereas in contrast the drug unstable in intestine will face problem of less bioavailability.

Principles of Sustained release drug delivery

The conventional dosage forms release their active ingredients into an absorption pool immediately. This is illustrated in the following simple kinetic scheme in figure 1.

The absorption pool represents a solution of the drug at the site of absorption, K_1 , K_2 and K_3 - first order rate- r_1 a e constant for drug release, absorption and overall elimination respectively. Immediate drug release from a conventional dosage form implies that $K_1 \gg \gg \gg K_3$. For non-immediate release dosage forms, r_1 a $K_1 \ll K_3$ i.e. the release of drug from the dosage form is r_1 a the rate limiting step. The drug release from the dosage form should follows zero-order kinetics, as shown by the following equation: $Kr^0 = \text{Rate In} = \text{Rate Out} = KeCd Vd$

Where, K : Zero-order rate constant for drug release- r^0 Amount/time,

K : First-order rate constant for overall e drug elimination-time,

C : Desired drug level in the d body – Amount/volume, and

V : Volume space in d which the drug is distributed in litre ⁴

MATERIALS

Metformin hydrochloride -Metformin hydrochloride was purchased from BMR Pharma & Chemical Suppliers, Hyderabad, Telangana, India. Provided by SURA LABS, Dilsukhnagar, Hyderabad., Gaur gum-Guar gum were purchased from Strides Pharma Science Limited, Bangalore, Karnataka, India, Eudragit - Degussa India Ltd, Mumbai, Xanthan gum-Xanthan gum were purchased from Strides Pharma Science Limited, Bangalore, Karnataka, India, PVP K 30- Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India, Lactose-Shakti Chemicals, Mehsana, Indi, Magnesium stearate-Signet Chemical Corp., Mumbai, Talc-S. D. Fine Chemicals Ltd., Mumbai, India.

METHODOLOGY:

Analytical method development:

Determination of Wavelength:

10mg of pure drug was dissolved in 10ml methanol (primary stock solution - 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). From this primary stock solution 1 ml was pipette out into 10 ml volumetric flask and made it up to 10ml with the media (Secondary stock solution – 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). From secondary stock solution again 1ml was taken it in to another volumetric flask and made it up to 10 ml with media (working solution - 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). The working solution was taken for determining the wavelength.

Determination of Calibration Curve:

10mg of pure drug was dissolved in 10ml methanol (primary stock solution - 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). From this primary stock solution 1 ml was pipette out into 10 ml volumetric flask and made it up to 10ml with the media (Secondary stock solution – 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). From secondary stock solution required concentrations were prepared (shown in Table 8.1 and 8.) and those concentrations absorbance were found out at required wavelength.

Pre-formulation parameters

The quality of tablet, once formulated by rule, is generally dictated by the quality of physicochemical properties of blends. There are many formulations and process variables involved in mixing and all these can affect the characteristics of blends produced. The various characteristics of blends tested as per

Pharmacopoeia.

Angle of repose:

The frictional force in a loose powder can be measured by the angle of repose. It is defined as, the maximum angle possible between the surface of the pile of the powder and the horizontal plane. If more powder is added to the pile, it slides down the sides of the pile until the mutual friction of the particles producing a surface angle, is in equilibrium with the gravitational force. The fixed funnel method was employed to measure the angle of repose. A funnel was secured with its tip at a given height (h), above a graph paper that is placed on a flat horizontal surface. The blend was carefully pored through the funnel until the apex of the conical pile just touches the tip of the funnel. The radius (r) of the base of the conical pile was measured. The angle of repose was calculated using the following formula:

$$\tan \theta = h / r$$

Tan θ = Angle of repose

h = Height of the cone,

r = Radius of the cone base

Table 7.1: Angle of Repose values (as per USP)

Angle of Repose	Nature of Flow
<5	Excellent
5-30	Good
30-40	Passable
>40	Very poor

Bulk density:

Density is defined as weight per unit volume. Bulk density, is defined as the mass of the powder divided by the bulk volume and is expressed as gm/cm³. The bulk density of a powder primarily depends on particle size distribution, particle shape and the tendency of particles to adhere together. Bulk density is very important in the size of containers needed for handling, shipping, and storage of raw material and blend. It is also important in size blending equipment. 10 gm powder blend was sieved and introduced into a dry 0 ml cylinder, without compacting. The powder was carefully leveled without compacting and the unsettled

apparent volume, Vol, was read.

The bulk density was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Bulk Density} = M / V_o$$

Where, M = weight of sample

V_o = apparent volume of powder

Tapped density:

After carrying out the procedure as given in the measurement of bulk density the cylinder containing the sample was tapped using a suitable mechanical tapped density tester that provides 100 drops per minute and this was repeated until difference between succeeding measurement is less than % and then tapped volume, V measured, to the nearest graduated unit. The tapped density was calculated, in gm per L, using the formula:

$$\text{Tap} = M / V$$

Where, Tap= Tapped Density

M = Weight of sample

V= Tapped volume of powder

Measures of powder compressibility:

The Compressibility Index (Carr's Index) is a measure of the propensity of a powder to be compressed. It is determined from the bulk and tapped densities. In theory, the less compressible a material the more flow able it is. As such, it is measures of the relative importance of inter particulate interactions. In a free-flowing powder, such interactions are generally less significant, and the bulk and tapped densities will be closer in value.

For poorer flowing materials, there are frequently greater inter particle interactions, and a greater difference between the bulk and tapped densities will be observed. These differences are reflected in the Compressibility Index which is calculated using the following formulas:

$$\text{Carr's Index} = [(\text{tap} - b) / \text{tap}] \times 100$$

Where, b = Bulk Density

Tap = Tapped Density

Table 7.: Carr's index value (as per USP)

Carr's index	Properties
5 – 15	Excellent
1 – 16	Good
18 – 1	Fair to Passable
– 35	Poor
33 – 38	Very Poor
>40	Very Very Poor

Formulation development of Tablets:

All the formulations were prepared by direct compression. The compositions of different formulations are given in Table 7.3. The tablets were prepared as per the procedure given below and aim is to prolong the release of Metformin hydrochloride. Total weight of the tablet was considered as 500mg.

Procedure:

- 1) Metformin hydrochloride and all other ingredients were individually passed through sieve no \neq 60.
- 2) All the ingredients were mixed thoroughly by triturating up to 15 min.
- 3) The powder mixture was lubricated with talc.
- 4) The tablets were prepared by using direct compression method.

Table 7.3: Formulation composition for tablets

INGREDIENTS	FORMULATION CODE								
	F1	F	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Metformin hydrochloride	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250
Gaur gum	50	100	150	-	-	-	-	-	-
Eudragit	-	-	-	50	100	150	-	-	-
Xanthan gum	-	-	-	-	-	-	50	100	150
PVP K 30	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Lactose	182	132	82	182	132	82	182	132	82
Magnesium stearate	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Talc	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
Total weight	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500

All the quantities were in mg

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The present study was aimed to developing sustained release tablets of Metformin hydrochloride using various polymers. All the formulations were evaluated for physicochemical properties and *in vitro* drug release studies.

Analytical Method

Graphs of Metformin hydrochloride taken in 0.1N HCL and in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer at 236nm and 240nm respectively.

Table 8.1: Observations for graph of Metformin hydrochloride in 0.1N HCL

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
0	0
2	0.132
4	0.264
6	0.348
8	0.489
10	0.593

Fig 8.1: Standard curve of Metformin hydrochloride**Table 8.2: Standard graph values of Metformin hydrochloride at 240nm in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer**

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
0	0
2	0.136
4	0.267
6	0.383
8	0.498
10	0.624

Fig 8.2: Standard curve of Metformin hydrochloride

Pre-formulation parameters of powder blend

Table 8.3: Pre-formulation parameters of Core blend

Formulation code	Angle of repose (Θ)	Bulk density (gm/cm^3)	Tapped density (gm/cm^3)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's ratio
F1	26.6 \pm 0.2	0.555 \pm 0.1	0.714 \pm 0.1	22.22	1.285
F2	26.0 \pm 0.3	0.384 \pm 0.4	0.434 \pm 0.3	11.53	1.130
F3	26.7 \pm 0.4	0.416 \pm 0.2	0.476 \pm 0.3	12.50	1.142
F4	25.1 \pm 0.1	0.476 \pm 0.3	0.526 \pm 0.2	9.52	1.105
F5	28.3 \pm 0.4	0.625 \pm 0.1	0.833 \pm 0.1	25.00	1.331
F6	24.4 \pm 0.4	0.521 \pm 0.3	0.631 \pm 0.3	17.39	1.121
F7	27.1 \pm 0.1	0.588 \pm 0.3	0.666 \pm 0.4	11.76	1.334
F8	25.2 \pm 0.1	0.277 \pm 0.2	0.312 \pm 0.2	11.11	1.127
F9	23.2 \pm 0.2	0.434 \pm 0.2	0.476 \pm 0.3	8.695	1.095

All the values represent n=3

Tablet powder blend was subjected to various pre-formulation parameters. The angle of repose values indicates that the powder blend has good flow properties. The bulk density of all the formulations was found to be in the range showing that the powder has good flow properties. The tapped density of all the formulations powders has good flow properties. The compressibility index of all the formulations was found to be below 25.00 show that the powder has good flow properties. All the formulations has shown the hausner ratio below 1.34 indicating the powder has good flow properties

Quality Control Parameters For tablets:

Tablet quality control tests such as weight variation, hardness, and friability, thickness, and drug release studies in different media were performed on the compression tablet.

Table 8.4: *In vitro* quality control parameters for tablets

Formulation codes	Average Weight (mg)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability (%loss)	Thickness (mm)	Drug content (%)
F1	498.32	4.0 ± 0.1	0.17	3.2 ± 0.05	99.47 ± 0.3
F2	496.54	5.5 ± 0.1	0.30	3.1 ± 0.02	98.89 ± 0.5
F3	497.54	5.0 ± 0.4	0.42	3.3 ± 0.07	98.35 ± 0.9
F4	499.67	4.5 ± 0.2	0.67	3.2 ± 0.03	96.12 ± 0.5
F5	498.38	5.3 ± 0.1	0.56	3.0 ± 0.04	97.56 ± 0.6
F6	497.46	5.4 ± 0.3	0.74	3.1 ± 0.02	98.35 ± 0.3
F7	498.50	5.5 ± 0.4	0.40	3.3 ± 0.02	98.40 ± 0.4
F8	499.79	5.4 ± 0.2	0.28	3.4 ± 0.05	97.84 ± 0.3
F9	500.03	5.7 ± 0.2	0.36	3.2 ± 0.03	99.64 ± 0.1

Weight variation test:

Tablets of each batch were subjected to weight variation test, difference in weight and percent deviation was calculated for each tablet. The average weight of the tablet is approximately in range of 496.54 to 500.03mg, so the permissible limit is ±7.5% (>500 mg). The results of the test showed that, the tablet weights were within limit.

Hardness test:

Hardness of the three tablets of each batch was checked by using Pfizer hardness tester and the data were shown in Table 8.4. The results showed that the hardness of the tablets is in range of 4.0 ± 0.1 to 5.7 ± 0.2 kg/cm², which was within IP limits.

Thickness:

Thickness of three tablets of each batch was checked by using Micrometer and data shown in Table-8.4. The result showed that thickness of the tablet is ranging from 3.0 ± 0.04 to 3.4 ± 0.05 mm.

Friability:

Tablets of each batch were evaluated for percentage friability and the data were shown in the Table 8.4. The average friability of all the formulations was less than 1% as per official requirement of IP indicating a good mechanical resistance of tablets.

Drug content:

Drug content studies were performed for the prepared formulations. From the drug content studies it was concluded that all the formulations were showing the % drug content values within 96.12 ± 0.5-99.64 ± 0.1%.

All the parameters such as weight variation, friability, hardness, thickness and drug content were found to be within limit

In Vitro Drug Release Studies

Table 8.5: Dissolution Data of Metformin hydrochloride Tablets

TIME (hr)	% Cumulative Drug Release								
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
In dissolution media 0.1 N HCL									
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.5	15.45	12.46	17.23	13.10	16.54	18.32	17.21	14.52	16.85
1	21.12	17.32	23..56	17.16	22.60	21.60	23.15	21.92	22.41
2	25.62	29.62	27.36	21.80	27.45	26.20	29.22	24.65	25.35
In dissolution media 0.1 N HCL									
3	29.40	33.25	31.48	28.25	34.49	34.45	35.78	30.56	29.26
4	31.78	42.50	38.56	31.62	41.32	39.55	44.25	46.87	37.67
5	47.36	49.45	44.84	36.87	48.82	43.87	49.45	56.42	45.51
6	53.45	53.92	49.59	45.55	51.27	50.25	53.65	68.80	58.19
7	60.98	58.62	52.65	49.20	59.50	53.32	58.58	70.28	60.78
8	67.70	61.31	57.12	52.45	60.23	58.56	62.56	73.84	65.62
9	75.45	64.23	61.56	58.56	67.54	64.63	67.56	75.69	75.89
10	79.56	69.47	66.25	62.25	73.40	69.56	74.87	80.23	78.56
11	85.54	77.60	73.56	68.20	79.36	72.78	77.55	87.30	80.87
12	96.32	87.14	78.34	75.36	83.25	98.72	82.84	90.33	95.30

Fig 8.3: Dissolution profile of Metformin hydrochloride (F1, F2, F3 formulations)

Fig 8.4: Dissolution profile of Metformin hydrochloride F4, F5, F6 formulations)

Fig 8.5: Dissolution profile of Metformin hydrochloride (F7, F8, F9 formulations)

From the dissolution data it was evident that the formulations prepared with Gaur gum as polymer were retard the good drug release up to desired time period i.e., 12 hours.

Formulations prepared with Eudragit retarded the drug release in the concentration of 150mg (F6Formulation) showed required release pattern i.e., retarded the drug release up to 12 hours and showed maximum of 98.72% in 12 hours with good retardation.

Whereas the formulations prepared with Xanthan gum retarded the drug release in the concentration of 150mg (F9 Formulation) retarded the drug release (95.30%) up to 12 hours (Required Time).

Finally Concluded that F6 formulation was considered as optimized formulation.

Table 8.8: Release Kinetics:

CUMULATIVE (%) RELEASE Q	TIME (T)	ROOT (T)	LOG(%) RELEASE	LOG (T)	LOG (%) REMAIN	RELEASE RATE (CUMULATIVE % RELEASE / t)	1/CUM% RELEASE	PEPPAS log Q/100	% Drug Remaining	Q01/3	Qt1/3	Q01/3- Qt1/3
0	0	0			2.000				100	4.642	4.642	0.000
18.32	0.5	0.707	1.263		1.912	36.640	0.0546	-0.737	81.68	4.642	4.339	0.303
21.6	1	1.000	1.334	-0.301	1.894	21.600	0.0463	-0.666	78.4	4.642	4.280	0.362
26.2	2	1.414	1.418	0.000	1.868	13.100	0.0382	-0.582	73.8	4.642	4.195	0.447
34.45	3	1.732	1.537	0.301	1.817	11.483	0.0290	-0.463	65.55	4.642	4.032	0.610
39.55	4	2.000	1.597	0.477	1.781	9.888	0.0253	-0.403	60.45	4.642	3.925	0.717
43.87	5	2.236	1.642	0.602	1.749	8.774	0.0228	-0.358	56.13	4.642	3.829	0.813
50.25	6	2.449	1.701	0.699	1.697	8.375	0.0199	-0.299	49.75	4.642	3.678	0.964
53.32	7	2.646	1.727	0.778	1.669	7.617	0.0188	-0.273	46.68	4.642	3.601	1.041
58.56	8	2.828	1.768	0.845	1.617	7.320	0.0171	-0.232	41.44	4.642	3.461	1.181
64.63	9	3.000	1.810	0.903	1.549	7.181	0.0155	-0.190	35.37	4.642	3.283	1.359
69.56	10	3.162	1.842	0.954	1.483	6.956	0.0144	-0.158	30.44	4.642	3.122	1.519
72.78	11	3.317	1.862	1.000	1.435	6.616	0.0137	-0.138	27.22	4.642	3.008	1.633
98.72	12	3.464	1.994	1.041	0.107	8.227	0.0101	-0.006	1.28	4.642	1.086	3.556

Drug – Excipient compatibility studies

Figure 8.10: FT-TR Spectrum of Metformin hydrochloride pure drug

Figure 8.11: FT-IR Spectrum of optimised Formulation

There was no disappearance of any characteristic peak in the FTIR spectrum of drug and the polymers used. This shows that there is no chemical interaction between the drug and the polymers used. The presence of peaks at the expected range confirms that the materials taken for the study are genuine and there were no possible interactions.

Metformin hydrochloride is also present in the physical mixture, which indicates that there is no interaction between drug and the polymers, which confirms the stability of the drug.

CONCLUSION:

The present research work envisages the applicability of polymers such as Gaur gum, Eudragit and Xanthan gum in the design and development of SR tablet formulations of Metformin hydrochloride. Over a period of 12h (F6) was obtained by the using Eudragit was successful in the formulation of matrix tablet and at the same time it is effective in retarding the drug release. Among all the formulation F6 shows that 98.72% release at the end of 12 h. The optimized formulation followed Higuchi's kinetics. The sustained effect and efficient drug delivery system was developed in the present study will maintain Metformin hydrochloride r levels better, which will overcome the drawbacks associated with the conventional therapy.

REFERENCES:

1. Pundir S, Badola A, Sharma D. Sustained release matrix technology and recent advance in matrix drug delivery system: a review. *International Journal of drug research and technology*. 2017 Feb 28; 3(1):8.

2. Kumar V, Prajapati SK, Soni GC, Singh M, Kumar N. Sustained release matrix type drug delivery system: a review. *World journal of pharmacy and pharmaceutical sciences*. 2012 Sep 5;1(3):934-60.
3. Jaimini M, Kothari AH. Sustained release matrix type drug delivery system: a review. *Journal of Drug delivery and therapeutics*. 2012 Nov15; 2(6).
4. Gandhi A, Hari Kumar SL. Recent Trends in Sustained Release Drug Delivery System.
5. Karna S, Chaturvedi S, Agrawal V, Alim M. Formulation approaches for sustained release dosage forms: a review. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res*. 2015;8(5):46-53.
6. Pundir S, Badola A, Sharma D. Sustained release matrix technology and recent advance in matrix drug delivery system: a review. *International Journal of drug research and technology*. 2017 Feb 28; 3(1):8.
7. Shargel L, Wu-Pong S, Yu AB. *Applied biopharmaceutics & pharmacokinetics*. McGraw-Hill; 2007.
8. Schall R, Müller FR, Müller FO, Luus HG. Bioequivalence of controlled-release calcium antagonists. *Clinical pharmacokinetics*. 1997 Jan 1; 32(1):75-89.
9. Abdel-Rahman SI, Mahrous GM, El-Badry M. Preparation and comparative evaluation of sustained release metoclopramide hydrochloride matrix tablets. *Saudi Pharmaceutical Journal*. 2009 Oct 31; 17(4):283-8.
10. Asghar LF, Mantha N. Design and evaluation of ethyl cellulose based matrix tablets of ibuprofen with pH modulated release kinetics. *Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*. 2008; 70(5):596.

11. Gothi GD. Study on design and development of sustained release tablets of metoprolol succinate. *Journal of Global Pharma Technology*. 2010 Mar 3; 2(2).
12. Basak SC, Reddy BJ, Mani KL. Formulation and release behaviour of sustained release ambroxol hydrochloride HPMC matrix tablet. *Indian Journal of M Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2006; 68(5).
13. Dhat S, Aphale S, Bagul U, Tagalpallewar A, Vanshiv S, N Shah. Effect of Two Different Diluents On Release Profile Of Aceclofenac From Sustained Release Matrix Tablets Using Gum Damar As Release Retardant. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2011;3(4):30713
14. Aulton ME. *Pharmaceutics: The Science of Dosage Form Design*. 2nd ed, London: Churchill livingstone; 2005.p. 296-298.
15. Poddar RK, Rakha P, Singh SK, Mishra DN. Bioadhesive Polymers as a Platform for Drug Delivery: Possibilities and Future Trends. *Research Journal of Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms and Technology*. 2010; 2(1):1-6.